

FAIRification strategy for eCREAM outputs

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

ARDC FAIR	Australian Research Data Commons – FAIR self-assessment tool
CHUV	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois, Switzerland
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CRF	Case Report Form
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EBRAINS	Europe's Research Infrastructure for Brain Research
EC	European Commission
eCREAM	Enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
ED	Emergency Department
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic health record
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Italy
FHIR	Fast Health Care Interoperability Resources
F-UJI	FAIR testing tool developed by the FAIRsFAIR project
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GO FAIR	Stakeholder-driven and self-governed initiative that aims to implement the FAIR data principles
HEALTHYCLOUD	Health Research and Innovation Cloud. Horizon 2020 Project
HL7 CDA	Health Level Seven International Clinical Document Architecture
ICD	International Classification of Disease
IPD	Individual Patient Data
IRFMN	Istituto Di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS, Italy
IT	Information Technology
LM	Language Model
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
MIP	Medical Information Platform
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OMOP CDM	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model
Orobix	Orobix Life SRL, Italy
SNOMED CT	Systematized Medical Nomenclature for Medicine–Clinical Terminology
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The eCREAM project addresses the critical need for continuous assessment and improvement of emergency departments to ensure timely and effective patient care. By leveraging electronic health records (EHRs) and advanced natural language processing tools, eCREAM aims to overcome the challenges posed by high patient volumes and staff shortages that hinder clinical research in emergency medicine. The project will develop new technical solutions to extract valuable clinical information from EHRs, creating high-quality databases on patients visiting emergency departments. To maximise the impact of these outputs for secondary research and policymaking, eCREAM is committed to ensuring that the data it generates are readily discoverable and accessible to researchers, clinicians, policymakers, and citizens. Therefore, eCREAM will adhere to the FAIR principles—making its data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

This document represents Milestone “M13 - FAIRification strategy for eCREAM outputs.” It explains the FAIR principles and their significance for the project, details the data workflows within eCREAM, and outlines the strategy that will be used to FAIRify the project’s outputs. The FAIRification approach is grounded in the FAIRification process defined by the GO FAIR initiative and incorporates recommendations specific to healthcare data workflows.

eCREAM overview

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the critical role of high-quality emergency departments (EDs) in ensuring timely and effective care for patients¹. Initial evaluations in the ED are vital for determining appropriate treatment and hospitalisation², significantly impacting patient outcomes and satisfaction³. This situation underscores the need for continuous assessment and improvement of ED performance using validated criteria, best achieved through clinical and quality-of-care assessment research.

However, conducting research in emergency medicine faces sustainability challenges due to the high volume of patients (60.000-90.000 patients access a medium-size ED per year) and staff shortages⁴, making ad hoc data collection impractical. Consequently, research has been mostly limited to large academic centres with dedicated resources.

Implementing the direct extraction of data from EDs' electronic health records (EHRs) presents a solution to bypass the need for dedicated data collection. However, extracting meaningful data from EHRs is complex, as much of the useful patient information is unstructured, such as free-text notes on symptoms and diagnoses.

To address this, the main eCREAM objectives are:

1) To develop innovative technical solutions to extract clinical information from both structured (organized and easily searchable data, i.e., demographic details, vital signs, diagnostic codes, medications and lab results) and unstructured data (free text or images, i.e., medical images and written narratives, including clinical notes, problem lists, discharge summaries and radiology reports) from EHRs. To achieve this, an IT solution will first be designed to extract reliable information from the existing, heterogeneous EHRs in use in different EDs. Secondly, a new multilingual electronic health record specifically for EDs (ED-EHR), designed to meet organisational, clinical practice, and clinical research needs simultaneously without additional burden on staff will be created. A common tool for both solutions will be an artificial intelligence-based natural language processing (NLP) tool.

2) To establish high-quality, highly structured, interoperable databases of clinical information on patients visiting EDs and to pilot the exploitation of the established databases in two relevant use cases: i) the assessment of the propensity of emergency departments to hospitalise a patient, and ii) the development of a dashboard to monitor the state of emergency departments and emerging epidemiological trends, to be used by citizens and policy-makers to improve the quality of care in EDs.

¹ Roberta Petrino, Luis Garcia-Castrillo Riesgo, and Basak Yilmaz, 'Burnout in Emergency Medicine Professionals after 2 Years of the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Threat to the Healthcare System', *European Journal of Emergency Medicine* 29, no. 4 (1 August 2022): 279–84, <https://doi.org/10.1097/mej.0000000000000952>.

² 'NHS England » Guidance for Emergency Departments: Initial Assessment', accessed 30 August 2024, <https://www.england.nhs.uk/guidance-for-emergency-departments-initial-assessment/>.

³ Reham Mostafa and Khaled El-Atawi, 'Strategies to Measure and Improve Emergency Department Performance: A Review', *Cureus* 16, no. 1: e52879, accessed 10 July 2024, <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.52879>; Elizabeth E. Austin et al., 'Strategies to Measure and Improve Emergency Department Performance: A Scoping Review', *Scandinavian Journal of Trauma, Resuscitation and Emergency Medicine* 28, no. 1 (15 June 2020): 55, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13049-020-00749-2>.

⁴ Louella Vaughan and Nigel Edwards, 'Emergency Hospital Services Are Closing Because of Staff Shortages', *BMJ (Clinical Research Ed.)* 383 (7 December 2023): e078766, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2023-078766>; Mathieu Boniol et al., 'The Global Health Workforce Stock and Distribution in 2020 and 2030: A Threat to Equity and "universal" Health Coverage?', *BMJ Global Health* 7, no. 6 (June 2022): e009316, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2022-009316>; Zachariah Ramsey et al., 'Decreased Nursing Staffing Adversely Affects Emergency Department Throughput Metrics', *The Western Journal of Emergency Medicine* 19, no. 3 (May 2018): 496–500, <https://doi.org/10.5811/westjem.2018.1.36327>.

3) To make the established databases FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) for clinicians, researchers, health policymakers, and citizens, while respecting the European and national legislations.

The eCREAM project thus represents a significant step forward in emergency medicine, aiming to break down barriers to research and enhance the quality and efficiency of ED care through innovative technological solutions and a commitment to Open Science.

Scope and objectives of the eCREAM FAIRification strategy

The ‘FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship’ were introduced in 2016⁵ to provide guidelines for making research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The principles emphasise machine-actionability, enabling computational systems to efficiently find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with minimal human intervention. FAIR data enhances the discovery and integration of knowledge, maximizes research impact, and ensures research efficiency, transparency, and sustainability, thereby improving research data management and preserving data for future use⁶. Moreover, they support the planning, execution, analysis and reporting of research.

eCREAM-generated databases will be of immense value to the scientific, clinical, and public health communities, emphasising data as a public good. It is therefore essential that effective data management and stewardship are in place to guarantee the quality and usability of eCREAM outputs. The overarching goal of eCREAM’s FAIRification strategy is to ensure that the tools and databases created for the eCREAM use cases meet the standards of FAIR and address the specific needs and challenges associated with healthcare data. The specific objectives are:

1. Increase the (re)-usability of data by a variety of users outside the consortium, including patients’ advocacy groups, clinicians, policymakers, and researchers.
2. Maximize the exploitation of the collected data for secondary research and monitoring activities.
3. Enhance accessibility to various end users by the integration of the eCREAM databases and services into the Medical Informatics Platform (MIP) using a multi-level operational access model.
4. Maximise data reuse by embedding eCREAM outputs into the European data sharing landscape, including the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
5. Ensure adherence to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other national data protection regulations.

By implementing these objectives, the eCREAM project aims to maximize the impact and usability of its data and services while ensuring ethical and legal compliance.

FAIR Principles overview

The FAIR guiding principles⁷ (Figure 1) were first drafted by an expert group consisting of researchers, funders, publishers and university representatives as a part of the Future of Research and Communications end e-Scholarship group (<https://www.force11.org/>)⁸ with the aim to increase the reuse of scientific data

⁵ Mark D. Wilkinson et al., ‘The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship’, *Scientific Data* 3 (15 March 2016): 160018, <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

⁶ Danielle Welter et al., ‘FAIR in Action - a Flexible Framework to Guide FAIRification’, *Scientific Data* 10, no. 1 (19 May 2023): 291, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02167-2>; ‘How To FAIR’, accessed 30 August 2024, <https://www.howtofair.dk/>.

⁷ Wilkinson et al., ‘The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship’.

⁸ A. Anil Sinaci et al., ‘From Raw Data to FAIR Data: The FAIRification Workflow for Health Research’, *Methods of Information in Medicine* 59, no. S 01 (June 2020): e21–32, <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0040-1713684>.

and provide a set of best practices for sharing data, respecting any ethical, legal or contractual restrictions. They apply to any data, metadata and digital objects or infrastructure that led to the data. Applying the FAIR principles means to make your research data findable (others can discover the data), accessible (data can be made available to others), interoperable (data can be integrated with other data) and reusable (data can be re-used for new research).

The FAIR principles have gained increasing attention all over the world. Funding agencies are incorporating these principles into their guidelines (e.g., EC Horizon Europe⁹) and research institutions are including them in their policies. The European Union (EU) published the first Guidelines on FAIR data management in Horizon 2020 in 2016¹⁰. FAIR data contribute to the transparency and reproducibility of research and enable researchers to contribute to open science with high quality research data.

These 4 principles should be applied during the entire data life cycle, and they are closely interconnected (Figure 1). Briefly:

- To be **findable**, metadata and data should be discoverable by both humans and machines. This can be achieved by describing data with rich metadata, assigning unique and persistent identifiers to (meta)data, and by registering or indexing it in a searchable resource, allowing data objects to be found at any point in time.
- To be **accessible**, data should be retrievable by authorised users through clear protocols. The user should know where the data is located, how they can access it, and under which conditions. To achieve this, the conditions and the process for access must be specified. Even if direct access is restricted, metadata should be accessible (for example through data repositories), ensuring usability and interoperability across different contexts.
- To be **interoperable**, data should be easily integrated with other data and tools, allowing for seamless use by machines. This is accomplished by utilising common standards and data formats, ensuring that data can be effectively used in various applications, workflows, and processing tasks. Data objects are interoperable only when their (meta)data is machine-actionable, uses shared vocabularies or ontologies, and is both syntactically analysable and semantically accessible. Interoperability (vocabularies, formats necessary to curate, standardise, and visualise specialised data) is the main limiting factor for FAIR-compliance¹¹.
- To be **reusable**, data should be well-documented and accompanied by an appropriate license, allowing it to be used and replicated in new research. Reusability is achieved when data and metadata are well-described to help others understand the data, thus enabling the data to be combined and applied to different contexts with minimal effort. Additionally, data objects must adhere to principles of findability, accessibility, and interoperability, and should include rich metadata and provenance for proper citation and integration with other data sources.

The FAIR principles are of paramount importance in optimising the long-term utility of research data, conferring benefits not only to the researcher, but also to colleagues, collaborators, and the wider public. Adherence to these principles ensures that data is not only accessible and interoperable, but also of high quality, thereby facilitating innovative research and societal advancement. The provision of a clear usage licence, such as Creative Commons, further enhances the potential for reuse, fostering a collaborative environment where data can be effectively integrated and applied across various fields. Ultimately,

⁹ 'Horizon Europe Programme-Guide', accessed 30 August 2024, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf.

¹⁰ 'Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020', accessed 30 August 2024, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf.

¹¹ Paul Guillot, Martin Bøgsted, and Charles Vesteghem, 'FAIR Sharing of Health Data: A Systematic Review of Applicable Solutions', *Health and Technology* 13, no. 6 (1 November 2023): 869–82, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12553-023-00789-5>.

embracing FAIR principles supports a culture of transparency and shared knowledge, driving progress and discovery for the benefit of all.

Figure 1. Overview of the FAIR Guiding Principles

A number of ongoing initiatives address the application of FAIR data principles. Two prominent ones are:

- The FAIRification framework¹², one of the outcomes of the FAIRplus consortium¹³, which consist of three components: (1) a reusable FAIRification Process that outline the main phases of a FAIRification activity, (2) a FAIRification template that breaks down key elements of the process into a series of steps to follow when undertaking a FAIR transformation and, (3) a FAIRification Workplan layout, that provides structure for organising FAIR implementation work tailored to the needs of a specific project.

- The GO FAIR initiative which defined a seven-step FAIRification process¹⁴ as a set of step-by-step operations that should be performed over data and related metadata to achieve its FAIRness (i.e., adherence to the FAIR principles). The process consists of the following steps: (1) retrieve non-FAIR data, (2) analyse the retrieved data, (3) define the semantic model, (4) make data linkable, (5) assign license, (6) define metadata for the dataset, and (7) deploy/publish FAIR data resource. This process focuses on data, but also indicates the required work for metadata alignment.

Adherence to the FAIR principles may prove challenging when handling sensitive data, such as health information, due to its inherently personal nature and the need to comply with data protection regulations such as the GDPR. The data to be collected in eCREAM falls within this category, as it is health data that

¹² 'A Framework for FAIRification Processes', accessed 30 August 2024, <https://fairplus.github.io/the-fair-cookbook/content/recipes/introduction/fairification-process.html>.

¹³ 'FAIRplus | Home Page', accessed 30 August 2024, <https://fairplus-project.eu/>.

¹⁴ 'GO FAIR - FAIRification Process', GO FAIR, accessed 30 August 2024, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/fairification-process/>.

contains personal information about individual patients. Consequently, while we can ensure datasets are FAIR, we must comply with regulations and safeguard data from unauthorised access.

eCREAM Data types and Processing

To meet the project objectives, eCREAM is developing three data workflows focused on clinical data from EDs across seven European countries: Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. The first workflow involves developing natural language processing (NLP) solutions to extract clinical information from electronic health records (EHRs) and create comprehensive databases. These databases will then be applied and validated through two key use cases: Use Case 1 (UC1) will assess hospitalization rates in EDs, while Use Case 2 (UC2) will create a real-time dashboard for citizens, hospital staff, and policymakers to monitor ED status and track emerging epidemiological trends.

Natural Language Processing

Data type: anonymised clinical notes derived from EHRs. Unstructured, retrospective data.

Emergency department EHRs contain data that have the potential to bridge the gap between the need for research and the availability of data for clinical research. A significant proportion of the useful information, however, is contained in free text notes that are written in an unstructured format by emergency physicians and nurses. These notes cover a range of clinical information including diagnoses, syndromes, signs, and symptoms. Large-scale language models (LLMs) that can accurately interpret natural language and extract information from unstructured texts are currently available, but their use in specific domains, such as medicine, remains limited.

In eCREAM, we will develop and validate a state-of-the-art language model (eCREAM_LM) for the six languages of the project. This language model will be able to interpret EHR contents and extract relevant information (metadata) to be used, for example, to make accurate analyses and predictions, notably for research purposes rather than for clinical use. Natural language processing (NLP) and text analytics involve using machine learning algorithms and artificial intelligence to understand the meaning of text documents.

eCREAM_LM is based on deep learning architectures and will be tailored to the typical notes made by emergency physicians and nurses to maximize the retrieval of high-quality data from routine practice. The development of an NLP system for the emergency medicine clinical domain requires a combination of unsupervised and supervised methods, based on a huge number (hundreds of millions) of words to train the artificial intelligence algorithm. The creation of the eCREAM_LM language model will thus entail training and finetuning different language models through exposure to both a massive amount (billions) of medical texts derived from the literature and a large quantity of non-annotated (millions) and annotated (5,000) clinical notes derived from EHRs.

The eCREAM_LM will be validated by assessing its concordance with a panel of experts in extracting crucial information from 3,000 clinical notes. This project task involves retrospective data collection. Of note, all the information collected as part of this task will be anonymised.

Data processing¹⁵: The foreseen data processing activities are represented in figure 2. It involves several steps to ensure the secure handling and anonymization of clinical notes from emergency departments participating in the study. In brief:

¹⁵ Guido Bertolini et al., 'Study Protocol - NLP-DeVal: Development and Validation of a Natural Language Processing Tool to Enable Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute Care Medicine: Retrospective Cohort Study', 19 April 2024, <https://zenodo.org/records/10996542>.

First, free text notes from the emergency departments’ EHRs will be extracted. These notes will then be securely transmitted to eCREAM’s local NLP platform, which has been specifically developed for the project, deployed in each participating hospital and connected to the hospital’s intranet. The platform will be integrated with the hospital systems via APIs that are accessible only within the hospital network, ensuring no exposure to the public Internet. The system processes non-anonymized texts by retrieving them from the local repository, sending them to the anonymizer which then removes any references to third parties (e.g., patients’ relatives or caregivers) from the notes, and returns the anonymized versions to the repository. The last action separates each note from the others belonging to the same patient's record. Subsequently, the anonymized notes will be securely transmitted to the Central eCREAM server, where they will be stored in encrypted databases before being sent to the eCREAM partners at Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) and Orobix Life (Orobix) for further development of the eCREAM_LM. The anonymized notes will also be shared with major European platforms for language resource sharing, including the European Language Grid repository (<https://live.europeanlanguage-grid.eu>), CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (<https://vlo.clarin.eu/?2>), and the European Language Equality initiative (<https://european-languageequality.eu>). The technical aspects of data processing and protection are described in Annex 4 of the eCREAM-NLP-DeVal protocol.

Figure 2. NLP data processing overview

Use case 1: Measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalise patients

Data type: pseudonymized administrative and organisational data from the ED EHR (e.g., time of arrival at the ED, triage code, number of available workstations, capacity to perform certain diagnostic tests, real-time crowding levels in the ED and in the hospital), and clinical data from the ED EHR and other patient records. Structured and unstructured retrospective data.

ED performance is characterised by a series of decision-making steps, ranging from rapidly defining the priority with which patients will undergo a medical examination (triage), to establishing whether they need

hospitalisation. The IT-solutions developed by eCREAM will be tested in Use case 1 (UC1), a scenario that is one of the most critical in emergency medicine, due to the possible adverse consequences in both management (related to inappropriate hospitalisations) and clinical terms (related to inappropriate discharge). The decision to admit or discharge a patient from the ED is influenced, among other things, by patient-specific factors (e.g., medical condition), physician-specific factors (e.g., self-defined risk thresholds), hospital-specific factors (e.g., availability of medical resources), and societal-specific factors (e.g., presence of healthcare services).

Improving the appropriateness of patient admissions is therefore of paramount public interest. Enabling centres to compare their performance with that of other centres, taking into account case mix and context, is a demonstrated approach that leads to improvements. Such comparison requires statistical models capable of accurately estimating the probability of patient admission as a function of patient and ED characteristics. Unfortunately, the models proposed in the literature are based on vague representations of patient conditions, essentially those available in administrative databases. The impossibility of relying on dedicated data collection due to the large number of patients treated in EDs and the chronic shortage of staff in these services has considerably limited the availability of accurate and reliable data. The only solution to bridge the gap between the need for research and the availability of high-quality data is to extract them directly from the ED EHRs.

In UC1 eCREAM will conduct an observational, multicentre, retrospective study to build adjusted indicator(s) for measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalise patients. The main objective of this study is to test the solutions for extracting structured data from different electronic patient records in a use case relevant to EDs. The analysis will focus on two subgroups of patients: those presenting to the ED with dyspnoea and those presenting following a transient loss of consciousness (TLoC). We will also investigate the association between the adjusted hospitalisation rate of different EDs and a short-term clinical outcome (i.e., 30-day survival) to test the possibility of extracting data from administrative records.

Two separate databases (one for each subgroup) will be created on all patients who presented to the participating EDs over a defined period, containing the information considered important to study both the propensity to hospitalise these patients and their 30-day mortality. Then two multivariable models that predict the probability that patients presenting to the ED with dyspnoea (first model) or after a TLoC (second model) will be admitted to the hospital, will be created to provide the participating EDs with an adjusted comparison of the hospitalisation rates for the patients with selected symptoms. While the indicators are not aimed at measuring the appropriateness of the decision, they will facilitate a revision of the clinical practice of the participating EDs to improve healthcare quality and outcome. Importantly, the participation of several EDs from different countries, and the possibility of pooling their data for analysis, will allow the study of the determinants of the disposition decision in terms of patients' clinical characteristics, organisational models, and their interaction. Knowledge of these determinants will be essential not only for improving the quality of individual departments that participate in the project, but also for directing policies to improve emergency medicine at large.

As described in the study protocol¹⁶, three types of data will be collected:

- Structural organisational data (at the individual centre level): Information about the capacity of each ED (e.g., availability of specific diagnostic tests without delays) will be collected through a questionnaire given to ED staff or department heads. This data does not include patient information.
- Transient organisational data: Data on all patients who visit the ED, such as real-time crowding levels in the ED and the hospital, will be collected. Only the necessary variables to calculate the number and type of patients in the ED at any time will be recorded.
- Patient characteristics data: For patients with dyspnoea or TLoC, specific variables needed to predict hospitalisation will be collected, as identified by an expert panel. This data will be automatically

¹⁶ Guido Bertolini et al., 'Study Protocol - Propensity to Hospitalize Patients from the ED in European Centers An Observational Retrospective Quality-of-Care Study', 19 April 2024, <https://zenodo.org/records/10996665>.

retrieved from existing EHRs without additional data collection from the centres. We refer to this list of variables as the eCREAM virtual case report form (vCRF).

Data processing: The process outlines how patient data will be identified, processed, and securely stored for the study (see Figure 3). In brief:

First, hospital information system managers will identify patients eligible for extended data collection (those visiting the ED for dyspnoea or TLoC) and those who are not. For non-eligible patients, only pseudonymised administrative data will be transferred to the central server via a specific interface. These data will serve to calculate the presence, at any given time, of patients in the ED and the timing of certain specific phases of the taking on of a patient. Then, for eligible patients, all data useful for the model (to predict hospitalisation), and therefore present in the CRF, will be sent to the Local eCREAM-UC1 Platform. This platform will first transmit structured data (such as lab results) to the Central eCREAM Server and then process unstructured text data into structured clinical information using the NLP system embedded in the local platform. The processed data will be transferred to the central server and combined with other datasets to form the UC1 study database.

After curation, the UC1 study database will be transferred to the Medical Informatics Platform (MIP) hosted by the CHUV on the EBRAINS Research Infrastructure in Switzerland. The MIP is a GDPR-compliant, privacy-aware platform that allows secure, federated analysis of clinical data. Three MIP implementations will be created: a public MIP for broader community access to dedicated anonymised data, an eCREAM MIP for accredited users within the eCREAM consortium, and an extended MIP federation, for partnering organizations outside the eCREAM consortium, who would like to join the project’s efforts, and agree to pre-process their data according to the established eCREAM data model. The data will be stored on the eCREAM project’s Central eCREAM server in Milan and on the MIP for a minimum of 10 years. After this period, all data will be permanently deleted unless specific authorisation is granted for extended storage by ethical authorities.

Figure 3. UC1 data processing overview

Use case 2: Development of a multipurpose dashboard for citizens and policymakers

Data type: anonymised clinical data obtained from EHRs. Real time data on all patients who visited the EDs between July 1, 2023, and December 31, 2023. Structured retrospective data.

Use Case 2 will develop three dashboards dedicated to citizens, healthcare providers, and healthcare policy makers¹⁷. The purpose of this study is to develop useful dashboards, not their implementation on real-time data. Therefore, even though the dashboards will be fed by data that are readily available in the databases of the participating hospitals, they will run on retrospectively extracted data. The data will originate from different hospital information systems, including the ED electronic health record and laboratory and radiology software. The aim is to extract the needed information from heterogeneous sources and to feed the dashboards according to the needs of the end-users. Overall, for citizens, the dashboard will be designed to enable them to choose the most appropriate ED to attend or to consider a different, more relevant or efficient health service; for healthcare providers, the dashboard will provide a clear and immediate picture of the ED situation in terms of patient flow and workflow; for healthcare policymakers, the dashboard will provide the ability to monitor specific phenomena of interest, such as ED crowding level, possible incidence of pre-specified epidemiological phenomena, availability and timeliness of primary and secondary patient transfers, ambulance offload delays, etc.

To this end, eCREAM will conduct an observational, multicentre, retrospective study. The local eCREAM UC2 platform, designed to extract information from the EDs' EHRs, will be installed in each participating hospital to automatically collect the data necessary to feed the three dashboards. The factual transmission of the data will be arranged only once. However, the Platform will be designed to be capable of generating, if necessary, multiple data transmissions. This is important to test the possible infrastructure that could be used in future projects if the developed dashboard will be proven useful. The data collected from the EDs will include administrative and clinical information, such as time of arrival at the ED, time of triage and visit, priority code assigned at triage, time of possible hospital admission, and any other data the panels of experts have decided to collect. Information on the EDs' organisational set-up will also be collected (e.g., the number of available workstations and the capacity to perform certain diagnostic tests). The local eCREAM platform will process the data, calculating the indicators necessary for the dashboards, aggregating them and thus rendering the data completely anonymous. Only the anonymised data needed to feed the three dashboards will then be transmitted from the participating centres to the eCREAM Central server for analysis.

In the final period of the study, the usefulness and appropriateness of the dashboards will be assessed by representatives of the three types of end-users through questionnaires and in-depth semi-structured interviews. The data collected through the questionnaires and interviews will be processed with the consent of the respondents.

Data processing: The data processing that will be carried out is represented in figure 4. The process outlines how data will be processed, anonymised, and transmitted to the study's dashboards. In brief:

First, the Local eCREAM UC2 Platform will be installed within each hospital's information system. Then, the necessary variables to update the dashboards will be extracted. The data will be retrospective and will concern patients who visited the ED in the six-month period in 2023. The data will be stored locally until processed and transmitted to the Central eCREAM server, after which they will be deleted.

The Local eCREAM UC2 Platform will calculate dashboard indicators, such as ED crowding levels or CT scan wait times. Since these indicators are, by definition, aggregate information, calculating the indicators corresponds to making the data completely anonymous. Once anonymized, the data will be securely transferred to the eCREAM Central server in Milan, for analysis. As controllers of their own data, the

¹⁷ Guido Bertolini et al., 'Study Protocol - Development of a Multipurpose Dashboard to Monitor the Situation of Emergency Departments', 19 April 2024, <https://zenodo.org/records/10996699>.

individual centres will be responsible for anonymization, through the Local eCREAM UC2 Platform, ensuring the data no longer falls under GDPR regulations.

Figure 4. UC2 data processing overview

FAIRification process

eCREAM’s FAIRification approach is based on the FAIRification process¹⁸ defined by the GO FAIR initiative¹⁹ as well as recommendations for FAIRification workflows specific to healthcare²⁰. Figure 5 depicts the process that we will use. Briefly, the FAIRification steps relevant for eCREAM are:

1. Analysis of the raw data (or assessment of current data and processes):

This step is concerned with the initial examination and understanding of data elements and their organization. It implies examining the actual content of the data to determine what concepts are represented, their structure, and storage format. Moreover, analysing health data requires incorporating clinical data models to ensure that the data aligns with established standards such as HL7 CDA, FHIR, Open EHR, and OMOP CDM.

Health Level Seven International (HL7) Clinical Document Architecture (CDA):	Standard for structured clinical documents.
HL7 Fast Health Care Interoperability Resources (FHIR):	Standards for exchanging healthcare information electronically.

¹⁸ ‘GO FAIR - FAIRification Process’.

¹⁹ ‘GO FAIR Initiative: Make Your Data & Services FAIR’, GO FAIR, accessed 30 August 2024, <https://www.go-fair.org/>.

²⁰ Sinaci et al., ‘From Raw Data to FAIR Data’; Guillot, Bøgsted, and Vesteghem, ‘FAIR Sharing of Health Data’.

OpenEHR:	Framework for electronic health records.
Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM):	Standard for observational health data.

These standards facilitate health data management and research repurposing. Additionally, various coding schemes and terminology systems must be considered during this analysis.

2. Data Curation and Validation:

This step aims to enhance the quality of the dataset for research. Unlike research-derived raw datasets, routine care health data must be curated (repurposed and validated) for research use. Data curation involves characterising metadata and extracting clinical concepts. The curated data should be validated against quantitative relationships and conform to the semantic data model defined for the FAIRification workflow.

Figure 5. FAIRification workflow for eCREAM data

3. Data pseudonymisation or anonymisation:

Data pseudonymisation and anonymisation are measures taken to FAIRify data that are unique to the health field due to the sensitive nature of data (individual patient data, IPD) subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR²¹) in the EU and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act²² in the United States, which prevents data from being openly shared. Once the dataset has been curated, validated, and the relevant metadata has been aggregated, the subsequent step would be to anonymise or pseudonymise the dataset, thus enabling its sharing without infringing the privacy rights of data subjects. The decision to

²¹ 'Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the Protection of Natural Persons with Regard to the Processing of Personal Data and on the Free Movement of Such Data, and Repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA Relevance)', 119 OJ L 5 (2016), <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>.

²² 'Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 (HIPAA) | CDC', 28 June 2022, <https://www.cdc.gov/phlp/publications/topic/hipaa.html>.

apply anonymisation or pseudonymisation to a given dataset will depend on the purpose for which the dataset was originally compiled.

4. Define the semantic model for the health data:

The objective of this step is defining the meaning and relationships of data elements in a formalised way that is actionable by computers. It implies creating a semantic model that accurately and unambiguously describes the meaning of entities and relationships within the dataset. It is essential that the definitions are actionable by computers and that they represent the consensus view within the domain. This will ensure standardisation and facilitate automated processing and interoperability. It is preferable to adopt and integrate existing standardised data models such as HL7 CDA, HL7 FHIR, or OMOP CDM. Furthermore, it is recommended to utilise established vocabularies and ontologies (e.g., ICD, SNOMED CT, LOINC) to ensure consistent and accurate semantic representation. The aforementioned conceptual models permit the classification of data models and data items in accordance with the provided terms, concepts, and conceptual structures.

Coding Schemes and Terminology Systems:

International Classification of Disease (ICD)	Standard for disease classification
Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT)	Comprehensive clinical terminology
Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC)	Standard for identifying medical laboratory observations

In the context of eCREAM, FHIR was identified as the most suitable data model for the eCREAM-EHR in Task T3.3, and we also plan to use FHIR for the APIs to ensure interoperability. Next, the interoperability modules will be developed, which will be based on adopting international communication standards for exchanging clinical and administrative documents and resources, which could be defined after the context analysis in the target EDs.

This first phase of the project focused on defining the workflow. The next step involves systematising the work done so far and further defining the ontologies to be implemented in the next phase of the workflow. FHIR and SNOMED have been taken into consideration. FHIR will be used as the standard for the database model. SNOMED was formally contacted with the request for free access, which was granted until the project's end.

5. Make data linkable:

Data can be made linkable by applying the semantic model defined above. This involves using semantic web and linked data technologies to enhance the data's discoverability and accessibility. By embedding standardized vocabularies, terminology systems, and coding standards, such as ICD, SNOMED CT, and LOINC, the data becomes more interoperable and reusable. This step ensures that data can be easily integrated with other types of data and systems, promoting seamless data sharing and utilization across different platforms and domains.

6. Assign license:

It is imperative that licensing attributions for sensitive datasets obtained from emergency departments comply with the regulatory framework applicable to each data owner. These licensing attributions define the process of granting permissions to use and access the data, as well as the permitted uses of the data. Furthermore, to guarantee the reusability of the data, it is vital that the licensing terms for the dataset are

clearly defined, along with the procedure by which external requesters can seek permission to reuse the dataset. This transparency is essential to ensure compliance and facilitate the ethical and lawful reuse of health data.

7. Data versioning:

Managing and documenting changes to data overtime are essential to maintaining integrity, reliability, and reproducibility of health data. It ensures that every modification to the dataset is tracked, and previous versions of the data are preserved and accessible. This step is part of the FAIRification workflow proposed in Sinaci et al.²³ Versioning helps to understand the evolution of the dataset, provides continuous access to historical data, maintains consistency between different versions, provides a detailed provenance of the data and improves transparency by allowing users to see how the data has changed over time.

8. Define metadata for the dataset:

Metadata is information associated with datasets and data files that provides context²⁴. It should be easy to find by both humans and computers, as machine-readable metadata facilitates automatic discovery of datasets and services. Metadata essentially describes the data, and it encompasses structured information that describes, explains, and contextualizes the collected data, including details about the study design, methodology, data collection protocols, variables measured, data processing techniques, and data provenance. Additionally, metadata should include comprehensive information on how and where the data can be accessed, including any necessary procedures for gaining access if the data is not publicly available. By enhancing the dataset's quality and understandability, metadata increases its findability, facilitates data sharing, improves research reproducibility, and enables secondary use of data. While many metadata standards exist, ECRIN has developed a metadata schema for clinical research²⁵, based on the DataCite standard, to address common needs in health research and serve as a foundation for the FAIRification of eCREAM datasets.

9. (Meta)data indexing and registration/storage in a searchable resource

Indexing refers to the systematic organization and cataloguing of data to enhance its discoverability and accessibility. By creating an index, data elements are tagged with relevant keywords and metadata, which are then stored in searchable databases or repositories. This process allows users to efficiently locate specific datasets or data points through search queries, significantly improving the findability of the data. Indexing is crucial because it ensures that data is not only accessible but also easily retrievable by researchers, clinicians, and other stakeholders, facilitating better data integration, analysis, and reuse while complying with the FAIR principles.

10. Deployment/publication of FAIRified data:

Datasets are made available. The FAIRified data is published together with relevant metadata and a license, so that the metadata can be indexed by search engines and the data can be accessed, even if authentication and authorisation are required.

²³ Sinaci et al., 'From Raw Data to FAIR Data'.

²⁴ 'FAIR and the Notion of Metadata', accessed 30 August 2024, <https://fairplus.github.io/the-fair-cookbook/content/recipes/introduction/metadata-fair.html>.

²⁵ Steve Canham, 'ECRIN Metadata Schemas for Clinical Research, Version 8 (September 2023)', 21 September 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368709>.

Implementation Workplan

In practice, implementing FAIR practices in eCREAM workflows requires specific actions and resources across the entire process, from data collection and management to storage and sharing. Figure 6 depicts a progressive workplan, which we have divided into five main stages of implementation. We also define some of the roles and responsibilities of project participants that are relevant to the implementation of the FAIRification strategy (Table 1). The various stages of the FAIRification process, after the preparatory phase which has already begun, will begin once the data is available. We will update the report at the end of the project with a full assessment of eCREAM FAIRness.

Stages of implementation

- a) Preparatory phase: covering the development of a data management plan, the submission of ethical approvals, and the initial set up of the local eCREAM platforms in the various EDs.
- b) Initial implementation phase: focused on ensuring the consistency of data collection across participating EDs. This phase will also involve robust data management practices, including data analysis and curation, the use of tools and software that enforce standardised data entry, thereby reducing variability in the collected data. Furthermore, a central eCREAM server will be implemented to centralise data from different EDs, ensuring that it is consistently formatted and easily accessible for further analysis and processing.
- c) Anonymisation, standardisation and interoperability phase: focusing on protecting patient privacy through data pseudonymization or anonymization while still making the data accessible for research and analysis. This phase also aims at the adoption and integration of established data standards, vocabularies, and ontologies to ensure that eCREAM data can be easily shared and understood across different systems. Additionally, tools will be developed to process unstructured data from EHRs, transforming it into structured formats that facilitate easier reuse and integration with other datasets.

Figure 6. Workplan for the implementation of the FAIRification strategy in eCREAM

- d) Accessibility phase: focused on ensuring that data is made available in a controlled, secure, and compliant manner to authorized stakeholders. The primary objectives here are to assign appropriate licenses to eCREAM datasets to facilitate controlled access while fully adhering to GDPR and other relevant access policies. This is supported by the implementation of a robust system to manage data access permissions, ensuring that only authorised individuals and organisations can retrieve and use the data. Additionally, this phase involves defining comprehensive metadata for each dataset, capturing essential details such as context and provenance, and assigning unique identifiers to all datasets. These steps are crucial for making the data not only accessible, but also meaningful, trackable, and easily integrated across various platforms, thereby maximising its usability.
- e) Data sharing phase: this is the final phase in which the results of eCREAM will be made available to stakeholders for secondary use. During this phase, we will set up platforms and APIs that will allow stakeholders to easily access the data through secure interfaces. We will develop and provide comprehensive documentation on the data and access procedures. This also involves indexing, recording and storing (meta)data in searchable resources to ensure that it can be located and used effectively.

Roles and responsibilities of project team members

The success of the FAIRification strategy in eCREAM depends on a collaborative effort involving a multidisciplinary team. This is because making data FAIR requires a range of expertise and capabilities, including highly technical tasks like data access control and ontology maintenance, aspects of data management such as the creation of data dictionaries, project-level governance and legal considerations, such as data licensing and reuse conditions²⁶. WP5 is leading this task and is supported by technical partners, data managers, legal advisors, and the project coordination team. Each one plays an important role, as described in the table below. However, the specific responsibilities and composition of the teams may evolve as the process progresses, and the skills required may vary.

Table 1. Roles and responsibilities in the FAIRification process

Who	Role	Responsibilities
WP5 team	Oversees the entire FAIRification process and ensures that all data-related activities align with FAIR principles and that the implementation strategy is executed effectively. WP5 is also in charge of ensuring compliance with ethical and regulatory issues, including the GDPR.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and enforce the data management plan • Coordinate different stakeholders, including technical teams, data managers and legal advisors • Monitor progress and report on the implementation of the FAIR principles • Review data management processes for legal and ethical compliance • Ensure that all data-sharing agreements align with legal requirements
Data Managers (data stewards)	Manage the day-to-day data handling tasks, ensuring that data collection, storage, and sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure accurate metadata creation and data standardization

²⁶ 'A Framework for FAIRification Processes'.

	processes adhere to FAIR principles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage data repositories and ensure datasets are correctly indexed and accessible • Work closely with the technical teams to implement interoperability standards.
Technical team (IT specialist and developers)	Responsible for setting up and maintaining the technical infrastructure required for FAIR data management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and maintain data repositories and access platforms • Implement and integrate tools for data extraction from EHRs • Ensure the technical infrastructure supports interoperability and accessibility.
WP5 and WP8 teams	Responsible for engaging with various stakeholders and providing training on FAIR principles and data management practices if necessary.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise training sessions for ED staff, researchers, and other stakeholders • Act as the primary point of contact for stakeholder feedback and support • Facilitate communication between the data management team and end-users.

Monitoring and Evaluation

To assess the FAIRness of eCREAM outputs, the following metrics are proposed, aligned with the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability:

Findability:

- Metadata completeness: number of datasets with complete and standardised metadata.
- Indexing/registration in repositories: number of datasets indexed in searchable and recognised resources.
- Assignment of unique and persistent identifiers: number of datasets assigned a DOI (or other identifier) for persistent identification.

Accessibility:

- Open access availability: number of datasets accessible without restrictions vs datasets behind paywalls.
- Compliance with access policies: number of datasets under controlled access.
- Metadata accessibility: number of datasets for which the metadata will remain available even if the data is no longer available.

Interoperability:

- Standardised Formats Usage: number of datasets using standardised data formats (e.g., HL7, FHIR).
- Use of controlled vocabularies: number of datasets annotated with shared vocabularies or ontologies.
- Compatibility: number of datasets that can be integrated or combined with other datasets.

Reusability:

- Quality of data documentation: number of datasets accompanied by thorough documentation explaining structure, usage and provenance.
- Licensing: number of datasets released under licenses that allow for reuse (e.g., Creative Commons).

Moreover, there are several resources that can be used to assess and monitor the FAIRness of the eCREAM datasets at any given time. These tools are structured in the form of questions aligned with the FAIR principles. Once the questions have been completed, a number or indicator is provided to show the FAIR level of the data. For example:

- ARDC FAIR assessment tool (<https://ardc.edu.au/resources/working-with-data/fair-data/fair-self-assessment-tool/>)
- HEALTHYCLOUD FAIRness evaluation tool (file:///C:/Users/mrujano/Downloads/FAIR_TOOL.html)

There are also tools designed to evaluate the extent to which a dataset and/or a digital object complies with the FAIR principles. For example:

- The F-UJI tool (<https://www.f-uji.net/index.php?action=home>)
- FAIR-Checker (<https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/>)

By regularly monitoring progress, these tools will help us to improve the FAIRness of eCREAM data, ensuring that they meet the criteria for effective sharing, reuse and long-term preservation.

Stakeholder Engagement

It is essential to recognise the importance of stakeholders in the context of data FAIRification, as they are instrumental in defining and implementing the FAIRification process²⁷. In the context of eCREAM, stakeholders and end-users include individuals, groups or organisations with an interest in or potential impact on the development, implementation or outcomes of the eCREAM initiative. As such, key stakeholders include, but are not limited to, consortium members, funders, healthcare professionals working in emergency departments, researchers in the field of emergency medicine, policy makers involved in healthcare planning and regulation, legal/DPO experts, citizens seeking information on emergency care services and international initiatives focused on improving emergency medical practices.

A full description of eCREAM’s stakeholders and engagement strategies has been described the project deliverable D8.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation (interim report). The following table provides a summary of the proposed engagement strategies by stakeholder group:

Table 2. Stakeholders and engagement strategies

Stakeholder	Engagement strategies
eCREAM consortium members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal communication and dissemination activities to ensure efficient project management, progress monitoring, team cohesion, and establish a foundation for a future community of practice • Internal networking including regular teleconferences with WP leaders to monitor activities and address risks, biannual Steering Committee meetings to review progress, General Assembly meetings to share results, and site visits to clinical centres as needed to assess data quality.

²⁷ Wilkinson et al., ‘The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship’; Sinaci et al., ‘From Raw Data to FAIR Data’.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training through workshops and webinars will be provided for ED physicians on implementing the project and performing individual data analyses and self-assessment
Scientific and emergency medicine communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External networking activities and meetings to exchange information, data and best practices with other projects and working groups in the different fields covered by the project • Establishment of collaborations to ensure the project's long-term sustainability • Open access publications, conference presentations and online dissemination channels will be used to further engage these communities • National workshop dedicated to ED healthcare professionals will be organized in each country during the final year of the project to present the results obtained and the developed ED-EHR
Healthcare policymakers and Regulators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of meetings and workshops at hospital, regional, national, and international levels with public health authorities to present findings and ensure readiness for uptake • Organisation of focus groups with policymakers to determine their needs and reactions to eCREAM outputs, particularly the control panel for decision-makers, and to gather feedback during the project's development • Consult regulatory bodies or authorities on issues related to information governance and patient data protection within healthcare as necessary
Ethics and legal Experts	Engage experts in ethics, legal, privacy and data protection through the external Ethics Advisory Board and DPOs from the different centres in the countries involved in order to ensure compliance with ethical standards and respects individual privacy rights
Patients, caregivers, patient organisations and citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The utilisation of non-scientific communication media, including press releases and mainstream and social media channels, will be employed to disseminate information regarding the progress and results of the project • Active engagement at meetings and events hosted by the consortium and other relevant stakeholders
Industry	Software houses with a demonstrated interest in the development of electronic health records will be engaged through ad hoc meetings with the objective of transferring the ED-EHR to the marketplace
Technology and data experts	Data scientists, information technologists and data managers with expertise in the development and optimisation of technical solutions for data extraction and analysis will be engaged on an ad hoc meeting whenever necessary
Funding agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress reports • Informative website • White papers and scientific publications

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Meetings with the EC to monitor the progress of the project
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Integration with European Data Sharing Initiatives

eCREAM is still in the initial phase, but as results are produced, the plan is to embed them into the European data-sharing landscape of the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Furthermore, the eCREAM partners have extensive experience in the development of open-access databases and repositories, including the ECRIN clinical research metadata repository and the eBRAINS medical informatics platform. They have also participated in numerous EOSC initiatives, such as EOSC-Pilot, EOSC-Life, EOSC4Cancer, and EOSC-Future. eCREAM will leverage its experience to develop a repository that will be uploaded to the open-source, GDPR-compliant MIP. This will enable other projects, researchers, and so forth to federate their data with eCREAM data and perform analyses on it. eCREAM repositories will be registered in FAIRsharing.org.

Conclusion

In the context of eCREAM, ensuring that the data is FAIR is essential to maximise its impact and utility across a diverse range of stakeholders. By adhering to the FAIR principles, eCREAM ensures that the valuable clinical information extracted from electronic health records is readily discoverable and accessible to researchers, clinicians, policymakers, and citizens. This facilitates effective data sharing and collaboration, enhances the usability of the data for secondary research and policymaking, and supports the development of innovative solutions in emergency care. Ultimately, FAIR data management enables more informed decision-making, improves emergency department performance, and will contribute to the future European Health Data Space, advancing both scientific knowledge and public health outcomes.